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Antiphase boundaries in bulk Ni-Mn-Ga Heusler alloy observed by magnetic force microscopy

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The antiphase boundaries (APBs) in Ni-Mn-Ga Heusler alloys with L2₁ ordering have been so far possible to observe only in the foils using electron holography. Here, we present the possibility to observe the APBs in bulk materials by conventional magnetic force microscopy using particularly oriented and magnetized single crystal samples in the martensite state. The bipolar APB contrast occurs where in-plane magnetization is oriented perpendicularly to APBs. This is in agreement with a qualitative model of an APB as a planar non-magnetic layer in the ferromagnetic matrix. © 2018 Author(s). All article content, except where otherwise noted, is licensed under a Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY) license (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).

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Heusler alloys with composition close to Ni₂MnGa belong to the class of ferromagnetic shape memory alloys exhibiting extraordinary magneto-mechanical effects such as giant magnetic field-induced strain (MFIS) or magnetically induced martensite reorientation (MIR).^{1–4} These effects occur only in low symmetry martensitic phases (monoclinic, orthorhombic or tetragonal) obtained by transformation from a parent, high temperature cubic L2₁ ordered phase called austenite.^{5,6}

Like any other ordered compound, Ni₂MnGa is expected to contain antiphase domains (APDs) separated by antiphase boundaries (APBs) formed during transition from the disordered to an ordered phase. The presence of APBs can be ascribed to the heterogeneous nucleation of an ordered phase. The order is maintained within each APD, but is depressed within the APBs. In the case of Heusler alloys, thermal antiphase domains and APBs are generated during the B2' → L2₁ ordering transformation^{7–9} occurring at temperatures much higher than the temperature of martensitic transition.

The antiphase boundaries can be considered as planar defects of finite width. Typically, the Heusler structure exhibits two kinds of APBs, corresponding to the lattice displacement vectors $\mathbf{R} = 1/2\langle 100 \rangle$ and $\mathbf{R} = 1/4\langle 111 \rangle$.^{8,9} Depending on their concentration, the APBs can influence various physical and transformation properties. In particular, the ferromagnetic parameters can be modified at APBs resulting, e.g., in an energy minimum for the magnetic domain wall (DW)^{10–12} enhancing magnetic coercivity.

Recently, it has been shown that the high concentration of APBs significantly affects the elastic properties of the Ni₂MnGa cubic austenite prior to transformation owing to enhanced magneto-elastic interaction and the suppression of already small magnetic anisotropy of cubic austenite.¹³ Even proper structural determination of complex martensitic structures can be hindered by the presence of small coherent antiphase domains causing diffraction peak broadening.⁶ Thus, the visualization and determination of antiphase domain size and antiphase boundary density is an important step in

understanding the material behavior, which can be influenced or even determined by the interaction between the APBs and ferroelastic and ferromagnetic domains.

However, the usual way to detect APBs is not possible in Ni₂MnGa. APBs are conventionally observed by two-beam dark field imaging in a transmission electron microscope (TEM). In Ni₂MnGa, the APBs are invisible due to the close atomic number between Mn and Ga and an anomalously large extinction distance of superstructure reflections. Lorentz TEM microscopy has been so far the only method, which allowed imaging of APBs in Ni₂MnGa thin foils.^{9,12,14,15}

In this letter, we report our finding that thermal APBs can be observed in Ni-Mn-Ga bulk single crystal samples under particular controlled conditions by means of conventional magnetic force microscopy (MFM) without the necessity to resort to TEM thin foils. The observation is enabled by the interaction of magnetization with the APBs. We additionally demonstrate nearly one to one correspondence between the APBs and a maze magnetic domain pattern which confirms the pinning of magnetic DWs on APBs in bulk materials.

The samples for measurements were cuboid {100}-cut Ni₅₀Mn₂₈Ga₂₂ (at. %) single crystals with dimensions of 1 × 2.5 × 10 mm³ from Adaptamat Ltd. At room temperature, they exhibited a five-layered modulated (10M) martensite structure, which for the purpose of magnetic studies can be considered as tetragonal with $c/a \approx 0.94$, where the short c -axis is an easy axis of magnetization. The samples were ground with a P4000 paper and then electropolished at 253 K in a Struers Lectropol-5 instrument. Prior to each set of MFM observations, the electropolished samples were magnetized by the field of 1.5 T along a selected principal geometrical axis. This caused MIR, i.e., the reorientation of the easy c -axis along the magnetization direction and the accompanying reorientation of magnetic domains along the direction of magnetic field.^{16,17}

The magnetic contrast was measured by an atomic/magnetic force microscope Dimension Icon by Bruker with MFM probes Bruker MESP-HR10, which are high-resolution, high moment probes with a cobalt alloy hard magnetic coating. According to the producer, the tip height

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is $5\text{--}7\ \mu\text{m}$, the radius of curvature after coating is $<40\ \text{nm}$, and the full cone angle $<12^\circ$. Coercivity (both in-plane and perpendicular) is $\sim 950\ \text{Oe}$, which is much higher than the coercivity of 10M martensite. The in-plane remanence magnetization is $\sim 540\ \text{emu/cm}^3$. The perpendicular remanence magnetization is $\sim 160\ \text{emu/cm}^3$. The magnetic moment of the tip is $\sim 5.6 \times 10^{-14}\ \text{emu}$. The distance between the tip and the surface was $30\ \text{nm}$ for low magnetic contrast, i.e., for magnetization in plane and $100\ \text{nm}$ for high magnetic contrast, i.e., for magnetization perpendicular to the surface (out-of-plane). The sharpest observations of APBs were obtained with fresh, previously unused MFM probes.

Figure 1(a) shows the surface topography of the sample with a uniform orientation of the c -axis after out-of-plane

FIG. 1. AFM/MFM observations on a sample with uniform orientation of the c -axis induced by prior magnetization (MIR): (a) surface topography (height and amplitude error were combined in one figure in order to improve the visibility of fine features), (b) magnetic domains after out-of-plane magnetization, and (c) APB contrast after in-plane magnetization with selected APBs being marked. The orientation of the magnetic field (1.5 T) applied before observation and of the c -axis are marked in (a)–(c). Yellow rectangles mark the region analyzed in detail in Fig. 2.

magnetization in a 1.5 T magnetic field. There are alternating smooth “valleys” and “hills” of height less than $\pm 20\ \text{nm}$ and a size of several micrometers in diameter. This smooth topography resulted from electropolishing. It did not correlate with magnetic contrasts and will not be further discussed. Additional features observed in topography were few minuscule “scratches” on the surface. Some of them are marked in the figure by arrows.

The magnetic contrast for the same spot and orientation as in Fig. 1(a) is shown in Fig. 1(b). Here, the magnetic domains are seen as a strongly contrasting maze pattern, which is typical for materials with large uniaxial magneto-crystalline anisotropy with the easy axis perpendicular to surface.^{18,19} This observation is in agreement with the magnetic properties of 10M martensite and the previous reports.^{16,17,20}

An MFM micrograph of an in-plane magnetized sample is shown in Fig. 1(c). Owing to MIR, the in-plane magnetization resulted in the easy magnetization c -axis being in the field direction and in plane. Therefore, in contrast to above, the magnetization vector now lies in plane. There are no maze magnetic domains and due to large magnification, neither 180° magnetic DWs are seen in the micrograph. However, a weak (comparing about $\pm 100\ \text{Hz}$ and about $\pm 2\ \text{Hz}$ contrast amplitudes in Figs. 1(b) and 1(c), respectively) but distinct curved pattern is seen. Some minor parts of this pattern were identified to be caused by the surface “scratches” [Fig. 1(a)], but the few linear surface scratches observed cannot explain the existence of a rich curved pattern. The curved pattern corresponds to APBs, as interpreted and discussed in more detail below and is hereafter referred to as APB contrast or APB pattern.

To study the discovered APB contrast further, detailed MFM micrographs are shown in Fig. 2 taken after magnetizing the sample in three perpendicular directions. The magnetization resulted in MIR and three different orientations of the c -axis and magnetization in the same sample. All micrographs show the same location on the sample surface. The curved APB pattern is well apparent in Figs. 2(a) and 2(b), showing the sample with two perpendicular directions of in-plane magnetization.

Figure 2(c) shows the magnetic domains after magnetizing the sample out-of-plane. Due to the magnetization orientation, there is no contrast arising from APBs. However, a careful comparison with Figs. 2(a) and 2(b) indicates that the magnetic domain pattern follows the APBs to a large extent, i.e., the magnetic domains are pinned on APBs. The interaction of magnetic domains with APBs and related domain wall pinning were previously observed by Lorentz TEM microscopy in thin foils.⁹ The correspondence between the APB pattern and the magnetic DWs, however, cannot be perfect in bulk. The APBs are three-dimensional entities and curve beneath the surface. Thus, the APB pattern at a certain depth below the surface is inevitably different from that observed on the surface but still can pin the magnetic DWs. The correspondence is further distorted by magnetic domain branching. In the bulk, the magnetic domains are much larger than on the surface as apparent from the analysis of a stray field using a magneto-optical indicator.^{16,17,21} In spite of these effects, the correspondence between the observed magnetic DWs

FIG. 2. Comparison of MFM micrographs showing APB contrast with an MFM micrograph showing magnetic domains within the same observed region (marked in Fig. 1): (a) APB contrast, field in-plane horizontally, (b) APB contrast, field in-plane vertically, and (c) magnetic domains, field out-of-plane. Figures (b) and (c) were re-scaled to compensate for the distortion resulting from MIR. Selected corresponding APB and magnetic domain shapes are marked in the figures by yellow rectangles.

and APBs is very good and can be found on many places in addition to indicated regions.

The comparison of the two MFM micrographs in Figs. 2(a) and 2(b) provides important information on the APB contrast: (i) it is perpendicular to the magnetization direction and there is no contrast along magnetization, (ii) the curved contrasts for the two perpendicular in-plane magnetizing directions complement each other, i.e., the contrasts clearly originate from different parts of the same APBs, and (iii) the contrast is bipolar, being lighter from the side where the magnetization crosses the line and darker on the other side. Such bipolar contrast is analogous to that observed when magnetization crosses the scratch line.^{18,19} This provides a

clue for the interpretation of the contrast. It arises due to the interaction of the magnetization with the perpendicularly oriented APBs.

The magnetic properties within the APBs are expected to be different in comparison with the matrix due to atomic disorder. The ferromagnetism can be diminished²² or rarely even amplified²³ and in the case of Heusler compounds containing Mn, antiferromagnetism can also appear due to atomic disorder and the varied distance between Mn atoms.^{24,25} The nonmagnetic or weakly magnetic character of the APBs in Ni-Mn-Ga is expected due to B2' disorder.^{9,26} The weakened magnetic moment within the APBs locally disturb the magnetization resulting in an out-of-plane stray field component near the APBs, which is detectable by the MFM probe.

Venkateswaran *et al.*⁹ modeled the APB as a planar defect with modulated magnetic properties within the matrix. For qualitative modeling of APB contrast, the APB can be considered being just a nonmagnetic layer within the ferromagnetic matrix. The magnetic behavior of the APB is then equivalent to the surface scratch line. In accordance with experiment [Figs. 1(c), 2(a), and 2(b)], we assume that magnetic domains are much larger than the discussed region, and thus the APB experiences uniform magnetization \mathbf{M} . The magnetization crossing the APB induces the magnetic poles on the relevant surfaces, Fig. 3(a). In other words, the magnetic domain is cut by the APB and magnetic poles of opposite signs appear at the APB edges. This generates the bipolar out-of-plane or stray field component seen by the MFM probe, Fig. 3(b). For the APB oriented perpendicularly to magnetization, the number of magnetic poles is the largest and they are close to each other resulting in a good line contrast. For the APB oriented along the magnetization, the magnetic poles appear only on a very narrow APB cross-section and are far apart. Thus, such oriented APBs are undetectable by MFM.

FIG. 3. Modeling APB as a nonmagnetic layer within the ferromagnetic matrix: (a) APBs oriented parallel and perpendicular to magnetization \mathbf{M} generate magnetic poles (s, n) on the relevant edges. (b) Expected MFM contrast for the two configurations in (a).

FIG. 4. (a) MFM micrograph of a surface with in-plane magnetization showing APBs and a single 180° magnetic domain wall. The directions of magnetization M are marked by yellow arrows. The magnetic DW is marked by dashed yellow lines. Pinning at APBs is indicated by red arrows. Short yellow lines indicate line scans. (b) Line scans (left-right, top-down) taken from (a) and comparison with model. The scans were re-scaled for the sake of clarity; in reality, the signal from DW is five times larger than from APBs.

To confirm the suggested model and to clarify how the APB contrast differs from the magnetic DW contrast, the detailed MFM micrographs including 180° magnetic DWs were taken. An example micrograph is shown in Fig. 4(a). The nearly vertical magnetic DW is indicated by the dashed rectangle. The domain wall separates two regions with opposite directions of magnetization and a reversed bipolar contrast of APBs. Moreover, it is apparent that the domain wall is pinned at APBs. This is accompanied by strong, dipole-like contrast. The change in the contrast also suggests a change in the chirality of the magnetization vector inside the wall after crossing the APB. This change in chirality was

observed previously,¹⁷ but no reason was given as no APB was detected due to a low resolution MFM figure.

Contrast line profiles, Fig. 4(b), clearly demonstrate the bipolar character of APB contrast and its dependence on the direction of local magnetization (profiles 1 and 2). The unipolar contrast from the 180° magnetic DW is seen as profile 3. The experimental profiles are in agreement with theoretical expectations shown also in the figure. The theoretical model profiles were calculated as the convolution of the magnetic tip and the stray field originating from the Bloch magnetic domain wall or in the case of APB, from the magnetic poles occurring on the edges of the APB (Fig. 3).

The width of the profiles is determined by the sensitivity and the resolution of the MFM, which is strongly affected by the distance between the magnetic tip and the surface and the tip size and tip radius.^{27,28} Due to the relatively large dimension of the magnetic tip with a radius of 40 nm, the measured profile is quite wide and thus the expected relatively narrow width of APBs cannot be evaluated. In any case, the width of the APB is much less than the width of the profile shown in Fig. 4(b). One can only roughly estimate that the width of APBs is of the same order or smaller than the thickness of the domain wall, which is about 10 nm in 10M martensite.¹⁷ This is similar to the estimation obtained from Lorenz microscopy and Foucault contrast.⁹

In summary, we observe the APBs in bulk single crystals of Ni-Mn-Ga 10M martensite using a conventional MFM microscope. For the observable APB contrast, the magnetization must be in-plane as the contrast arises from the interaction between magnetization and APBs. The contrast is very weak and can be drowned in strong magnetic domain contrast and thus usually invisible. The discovered method for APB visualization in bulk Ni-Mn-Ga Heusler alloys provides a tool to study the interaction of APBs, magnetic domain walls and twin boundaries important for understanding MIR and other magnetic or nonmagnetic behavior of the material.

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